

The Achievement Motives & Attitude towards Teaching Profession of the Secondary School Teachers in West Bengal

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ABSTRACT : The teacher is the most important element of an education system. The teacher's personal characteristics, his/her proficiency as the manager of learning activities, skills in monitoring the learning process and in teaching, background, and relations with students and other individuals influence his/her study and success within the classroom. Achievement motives are general characteristics of a person and since they are learned motives, their strength differs greatly from one individual to other. Another important factor that affects a teacher's success and efficiency is his/her attitude towards the profession. Every teacher is of his own social learnedness and based on that they exhibit different attitude towards their teaching profession and in their classrooms. The purpose of the study was to investigate the degree of achievement motives and attitude towards teaching profession of the secondary school teachers in Burdwan district of West Bengal. The study was conducted on one motive and on one trait in two categorical variables upon 130 secondary school teachers. The two major variables were achievement motive and attitude of teachers towards the teaching profession and the two categorical variables was gender (male & female) and location (rural & urban). The 'Achievement Motive' sub-scale under Social Motive Scale (SMS), by Dr. Ram Nayan Singh and Dr. Mahesh Bhargava (2005) and 'Attitude towards Teaching Profession' sub-scale under Teacher Attitude Inventory (TAI) by Dr. S. P. Ahluwalia (2007) were used in the study. The results showed that there exist significant differences between rural school teachers and urban school teachers in their attitude towards teaching profession and there exist significant relationship between attitude towards teaching profession and acceptance ach-m of achievement motive.

Keywords : Achievement motives, Attitude towards Teaching Profession.

Introduction

In modern world, attitudes of people are considered more important than their

experiences and academic preparation. In that sense a positive attitude towards teaching profession is a key to success and progress in

the knowledge based societies. Achievement motives are one of the components of social motives and otherwise known as acquired or learned motives. These are some complex forms of motives, which result mainly from man's interaction with his social environment. These motives are called social because they are learned in social groups. These peculiar human motives can be looked upon as general states that lead to particular behaviors. Social motives are general characteristics of a person and since they are learned motives, their strength differs greatly from one individual to other. It is unique to one and depends upon ways of perceiving things.

The quality and performance of teachers are always considered as determining factors for the success of educational changes. Since the 1980s, the decline in quality of teachers has become an issue of concern to the education sector worldwide (Ballou & Podgursky, 1997). Scholars and educators have identified several major problems faced by recruitment and retention in the teaching profession, such as the teaching profession fails to attract bright young people (Murnane, 1991), a disproportionate share of higher ability teachers leave teaching to pursue for other careers (Ballou & Podgursky, 1997; Murnane, 1991), and the under-representation of both qualified minority teachers (Newby, Smith, Newby, & Miller, 1995) and males in the primary school teaching force (Johnston, Mckeown, & McEwen, 1999). It is obvious that the quality of teaching force is not governed only by the qualification, pedagogical knowledge and teaching skill of teachers, but also their attitude, enthusiasm, dedication and commitment in teaching. It is determined by the social motives of teachers to conduct the teaching and how they perceive teaching

attitudes in the classrooms. At the same time, the teachers' behaviour and teaching performance may also be influenced by their conceptions about teaching and learning and their confidence to teach which the part of their motivation is. Thus it is important to examine all these psychological constructs of teachers under the umbrella of social motives of the teachers and to relate it with the attitude of the teachers towards their profession.

Natrajan, S (1988) in her thesis work explored the need motivation of student learners. Her objectives were to study the relationship between the four need motivation: n-Achievement, n-Affiliation, n-Power and n-Approval and to study the nature of the above mentioned four levels of student learners on various backgrounds in the Chhattisgarh region. She found there was no significant territorial variation on either of the four need motivation as well as authoritarianism between the four levels of student learners. A significant difference between graduate and post-graduate students was observed on n-Ach.

Deborah Mary LaBelle (2008) to her dissertation paper investigated the use of McClelland's social motives of power, achievement, and affiliation to that work in a semi-virtual environment. The study seeks to determine if such teams exhibit trust and perform successfully while working in an online environment. Separate analysis form teams of the two data sets determined whether social motive strength, social motive satisfaction and team construction by social motive strength showed significant correlation with trust and performance. The analysis showed that the formation of these semi-virtual teams by social motives influenced trust and team performance

for the chemistry data set, but further research is needed to verify and expand these results. No significant results were found for the English data set.

Maria de Lourdes Mata's (2012) paper aims to understand how certain different but interrelated variables such as background, motivation, and social support could lead to an explanation of teachers' attitudes towards teaching math and to an understanding of the defining characteristics of these attitudes in the school environment. The study utilizes an adaptation of the "Intrinsic Motivation Inventory" assessing main determinants of intrinsic motivation. The results revealed that, in general, teachers held positive attitudes towards teaching mathematics and also highlighted the main effects of grade and math teaching achievement on these attitudes. A hierarchical analysis using structural equation modeling showed that motivation-related variables are the main predictors of attitudes towards mathematics and that teachers and the social support of colleagues are also highly significant in understanding these attitudes.

Oral (2004), in his study about the attitudes of the teachers at the faculty of education towards the profession of teaching, used the scale which was originally developed by Semerci and Semerci (1999) in order to measure the attitudes of teachers towards the profession of teaching. A significant difference was observed between the attitudes of the teachers in the Faculty of Education towards the profession of teaching according to gender, the order of the program they attend in the preference list, and the reason for choosing the profession of teaching.

Das, B (1988) studied secondary school teachers' job satisfaction and job motivation in Cuttack district of Orissa. Her objectives was to study the extent of job satisfaction in and motivation of : i) rural and urban teachers, ii) trained and untrained teachers, iii) male and female teachers, iv) government school and private school teachers, and v) teachers from different age groups. Her findings were – Teachers who were motivated were also found highly satisfied in their jobs, 92% rural and 24% urban teachers, 62% trained and 46% untrained teachers, 53% male and female teachers, 77% government, and 25% private school teachers are satisfied with their jobs.

Objectives of the Study

1. To compare the achievement motives under different categorical variables, viz., Gender and Location.
2. To compare the attitude towards teaching profession under different categorical variables, viz., Gender and Location.
3. To compare the relationship between achievement motive with attitude towards teaching profession of the secondary school teachers.

The Hypotheses

H₀1: There would be no significant difference between female teachers and male teachers in their achievement motives.

H₀2: There would be no significant difference between rural school teachers and urban school teachers in their achievement motives.

H₀3: There would be no significant difference between female teachers and male teachers in their attitude towards the teaching profession.

H₀4: There would be no significant difference between the rural school teachers and urban school teachers in their attitude towards the teaching profession.

H₀5: There would be no significant relationship between the acceptance achievement motive and attitude of the teachers towards their teaching profession.

H₀6: There would be no significant relationship between the avoidance achievement motive and attitude of the teachers towards their teaching profession.

Methodology

Design

The quantitative approach was used by the present researcher as it was the most appropriate design for this research. The investigation was reductionistic in nature. The study employed a survey design also in which surveys were conducted by the present researcher personally to collect all the data from the respondent teachers.

Variables

Major variables – Achievement motives and Teachers' attitude towards teaching profession.

Categorical variables –

- i) Gender (Male-Female) and
- ii) Location (Urban-Rural)

Population & Sample

The population of the study was all secondary school teachers of West Bengal, teaching in the secondary schools under control of West Bengal Board of Secondary Education (WBBSE).

The present researcher had selected a total of 26 schools as samples, among those 13 urban schools and 13 rural schools were selected with the help of convenient sampling and five (5) teachers from each school by random selection as his sample. There were 62 female teachers and 68 male teachers and among those there were 69 rural teachers and 61 urban teachers out of a total 130 teachers as of his sample. The

Table 1: Sample frame of the Schools

Total number of Schools = 26			
Number of Rural Schools	Total - 13		
Type of Schools	Boys' School	Girls' School	Co-Ed School
Number of Schools	6	5	2
Number of Urban Schools	Total - 13		
Type of Schools	Boys' School	Girls' School	Co-Ed School
Number of Schools	4	5	4

Table 2: Sample frame of the Teachers

Total number of Teachers = 130		
Number of Female teachers	Total – 62	
	Rural - 26	Urban – 36
Number of Male teachers	Total – 68	
	Rural - 40	Urban – 28

sample frames are shown below in Table 1 and Table 2 respectively:

Tools

In measuring Achievement Motives of the secondary school teachers, one sub-scale of the standardized scale, Social Motive Scale (SMS), by Dr. Ram Nayan Singh, Ghazipur and Dr. Mahesh Bhargava, Agra (2005) of National Psychological Corporation, Agra was used. In this scale two consecutive statements were given. The respondent had to read both the statements (a & b) and then to tick (✓) any one alternative among those. After that they had to choose their degree of preferences from the 3 alternatives (Less, Sufficient & More) by ticking (✓) only.

To measure Attitude of the secondary school teachers towards teaching profession, one sub-scales of the standardized scale, Teacher Attitude Inventory (TAI), by Dr. S. P. Ahluwalia, Sagar (2007) of National Psychological Corporation, Agra was adapted with the help of the concerned supervisor of the present researcher named ‘Attitude towards Teaching Profession’. That inventory was a 90 item Likert instrument

consisting of six sub-scales. Each scale has 15 statements that pertains a particular aspect of prospective and practicing teacher’s professional attitudes. The present researcher took only the first sub-scale, i.e., ‘Attitude towards Teaching Profession’ that contains 15 items.

Scoring Procedure

For the ‘Achievement Motives Scale’, Stimulus conditions related to M_s component (+ve pole) and M_{af} component (-ve pole) has been placed between the 12 items of the questionnaire. To obtain raw scores, instructions were followed by the given scoring key and each raw score was converted in Sten score with the help of the Norm table provided by the scale.

For ‘Attitude towards Teaching Profession’ scale, Likert continuum - strongly agree, agree, undecided, disagree and strongly disagree had been provided to each item. Each item alternative was assigned a weight ranging from 4 (strongly agree) to 0 (strongly disagree) for favourable items and in the case of unfavourable items the range of weight was reversed i.e. from 0 (strongly agree) to 4 (strongly disagree).

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics – Attitude towards teaching profession

		Statistic	Std. Error	
Attitude Towards Teaching Profession	Mean	44.0231	0.44460	
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	43.1434	
		Upper Bound	44.9027	
	Median	44.0000		
	Variance	25.697		
	Std. Deviation	5.06923		
	Skewness	-0.136	0.212	
Kurtosis	-0.234	0.422		

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics – Achievement Motive

		Statistic	Std. Error
Acceptance Ach-m	Mean	2.41	0.071
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	2.27
		Upper Bound	2.55
	Median	2.00	
	Variance	0.662	
	Std. Deviation	0.814	
	Skewness	0.610	0.212
Kurtosis	-0.214	0.422	
Avoidance Ach-m	Mean	7.70	0.081
	95% Confidence Interval for Mean	Lower Bound	7.54
		Upper Bound	7.86
	Median	8.00	
	Variance	0.863	
	Std. Deviation	0.929	
	Skewness	-0.543	0.212
Kurtosis	0.021	0.422	

Presentation of Data

The presentation of data, collected by the present researcher was done in order to make inferences and generalizations about the population. After that data were tabulated and descriptive statistics were computed. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) Version 20.0 was used for this purpose. In the following segment these are depicted briefly.

Results

The collected data were been analyzed through SPSS 20.0 version and prior to that the Shapiro-Wilk test of normality was tested at 0.05 level.

The table 6 shows that t values are -1.580 and -0.264 respectively, calculated for female and male school teachers for the case of

Table 5: Group Statistics – Achievement Motive & Gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Acceptance Ach-m	Female	62	2.29	0.755	0.096
	Male	68	2.51	0.855	0.104
Avoidance Ach-m	Female	62	7.68	0.954	0.121
	Male	68	7.72	0.912	0.111

Table 6: Independent Sample Test – Achievement Motive & Gender

	Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Acceptance Ach-m	3.399	0.968	-1.580**	128	0.117
			-1.589	127.8	0.115
Avoidance Ach-m	0.393	0.532	-0.264**	128	0.792
			-0.263	125.5	0.793

** Not significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 7: Group Statistics – Achievement Motive & Location

	Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Acceptance Ach-m	Rural	69	2.42	0.864	0.104
	Urban	61	2.39	0.759	0.097
Avoidance Ach-m	Rural	69	7.58	0.898	0.108
	Urban	61	7.84	0.954	0.122

Table 8: Independent Sample Test – Achievement Motive & Location

	Levene’s Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Acceptance Ach-m	1.646	0.202	0.187**	128	0.852
Avoidance Ach-m	0.068	0.794	-1.579**	128	0.117

Acceptance Ach-m and Avoidance Ach-m with df 128 and p values are 0.117 ($p > 0.05$) and 0.792 ($p > 0.05$) respectively, hence the H_01 is not rejected here. Then it can be said that, there exist no significant difference between female teachers and male teachers in their achievement motive both for the case of acceptance and avoidance domain.

The table 8 shows that t values are 0.187 and -1.579 respectively, calculated for rural and urban school teachers for the case of

Acceptance Ach-m and Avoidance Ach-m with df 128 and p values are 0.852 ($p > 0.05$) and 0.117 ($p > 0.05$) respectively, hence the H_02 is not rejected ($p > 0.05$) here. Then it can be said that, there exist no significant difference between rural school teachers and urban school teachers in their achievement motive both for the case of acceptance and avoidance domain.

The table 10 shows that t value is 0.395, calculated for female and male school teachers with df 128 and p value is 0.694 ($p > 0.05$), hence

Table 9: Group Statistics - Attitude towards Teaching Profession – Gender

	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Attitude Towards Teaching Profession	Female	62	43.8387	5.31374	0.67485
	Male	68	44.1912	4.86921	0.59048

Table 10: Independent Sample Test - Attitude towards Teaching Profession – Gender

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Attitude Towards Teaching Profession	0.007	0.933	-0.395**	128	0.694

**Not significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

Table 11: Group Statistics - Attitude towards Teaching Profession – Location

	Location	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Attitude Towards Teaching Profession	Rural	69	45.0725	4.83041	0.58151
	Urban	61	42.8361	5.10940	0.65419

Table 12: Independent Sample Test - Attitude towards Teaching Profession– Location

	Levene's Test for Equality of Variance		t-test for Equality of Means		
	F	Sig	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Attitude Towards Teaching Profession	0.349	0.0556	2.564*	128	0.012

*Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

the H_{03} is not rejected here. Then it can be said that, there exist no significant difference between female school teachers and male school teachers in their attitude towards teaching profession.

The table 12 shows that t value is 2.564, calculated for rural and urban school teachers with df 128 and p value is 0.012 ($p < 0.05$), hence the H_{04} is rejected here. Then it can be said that, there exist significant difference between

rural school teachers and urban school teachers in their attitude towards teaching profession.

The table 14 shows that the Pearson Correlation coefficient (r), calculated for attitude towards teaching profession and acceptance ach-m of achievement motive, is 0.203, which is significant at the 0.05 level as the p value is 0.021 ($p < 0.05$) and showing weak correlation. The Pearson Correlation coefficient (r), calculated for attitude towards teaching

Table 13: Descriptive Statistics - Attitude towards Teaching Profession & Achievement Motive

	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Attitude towards Teaching Profession	44.0231	5.06923	130
Acceptance Ach-m	2.41	0.814	130
Avoidance Ach-m	7.70	0.929	130

Table 14: Correlation - Attitude towards Teaching Profession & Achievement Motive

		Acceptance Ach-m	Avoidance Ach-m
Attitude towards Teaching Profession	Pearson Correlation	0.203*	0.069**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.021	0.435
	N	130	130

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

**Correlation is not significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

profession and avoidance ach-m of achievement motive is 0.069, which is not significant at the 0.05 level and showing very weak correlation and p value is 0.435 ($p > 0.05$). Hence the H_05 is rejected and H_06 is not rejected in this case. Here it can be said that, there exist significant relationship between attitude towards teaching profession and acceptance ach-m of achievement motive but there exist no significant relationship between attitude towards teaching profession and avoidance ach-m of achievement motive.

Discussion

While to compare the achievement motive between female and male school teachers and rural and urban school teachers in their achievement motivation of the selected areas, the researcher didn't get any difference between them in their achievement motivation. This can

clearly indicate that male teachers and female teachers are both accepting responsibility for one's success or failure, always interested to know from others as to how he/she has done, are attempting to excel someone and trying to show something unusual.

When it was compared the attitude of the female and male school teachers towards their teaching profession, no significant difference was observed between them but when it was between rural and urban school teachers, significant difference was observed towards their attitude in their teaching profession. As attitudes are more general in terms of the effects in an individual's reactions against a group of events at a larger-scale or human communities, then it can be said that the effects of individual reaction or the better human community had led to the attitude of the teachers to their teaching profession.

The correlation between attitude of the teachers towards teaching profession and achievement motive shows the dual characteristic features of the secondary school teachers irrespective of gender and location of their schools. The correlation between attitude towards teaching profession and acceptance achievement social motive (Ach-m) shows significant correlation, which means the teachers who hope to win difficulties and achieve standard of excellence in their life also show good attitude towards their teaching profession. Added with that their positive social interactions with environment also influence their attitude and values to their profession which ultimately help the students in their classes. But the present

researcher could not find any correlation between avoidance achievement social motive and attitude of the teachers to their teaching profession. This could indicate the teachers who try to avoid or have the fear tendencies of being unsuccessful in gaining goals in their social life, do not mingle their these social characteristics with their attitude towards their teaching profession, which is very good sign for any teacher and at the same time for the students of those teachers in any institution.

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